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DEVELOPMENT AND METHOD VALIDATION OF RP-HPLC METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION AND FORCED DEGRADATION OF CEFOPERAZONE AND TAZOBACTAM IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

Objective: A new precise, accurate, sensitive and robust reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed for Cefoperazone and Tazobactam in marketed preparation. Method: The Chromatographic separation was achieved on Thermo BDS Hypersil C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm i.d. 5 μ) at ambient temperature. A Binary mobile phase consisting of 10 mM potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer, pH 2.8 and Acetonitrile (80:20, v/v) was delivered through a column at a flow rate of 1 ml/min. Estimation was performed at a coveted wavelength of 254 nm. Result: The method was linear over the concentration range of 40-200 μg/ml and correlation coefficient (r^2) was found to be 0.9997 for Cefoperazone (CEFO) and 5-25 μg/ml for Tazobactam (TAZO), correlation coefficient was found to be 0.9996. The retention times of the CEFO and TAZO were found to be 3.667 min and 4.737 min. respectively. The percentage content for Cefoperazone 98.94±1.0 and of Tazobactam was 99.69±0.96 in the marketed formulation. The low value of % Relative Standard Deviation (%RSD) was 0.224 and 0.018 for Cefoperazone and Tazobactam, respectively, indicates the reproducibility of this method. The low value of Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of quantitation (LOQ) suggests the sensitiveness of method. Conclusion: It can be concluded from the outcomes that the proposed RP-HPLC method was found to be simple, basic, accurate, robust and precise for the normal analysis of Cefoperazone and Tazobactam in bulk and sterile dried injection dosage forms. This method was validated as per ICH guidelines.

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INTRODUCTION

Irresistible illnesses have constantly been made the hazard to individual and creatures therefore, the treatment is obligatory utilizing appropriate antimicrobial agents.[1] Albeit diverse anti-infection agents have been produced however cephalosporin assembly of anti-infection agents are extensively used.[2] Cefoperazone is a third era cephalosporin anti-microbial displayed for the treatment of patients tainted with defenseless strains of microorganisms like respiratory tract, skin and delicate tissue, bone and joint diseases, septicemia, meningitis.[3] Cefoperazone (CEFO) is chemically [6R-[6 α ,7 β (R)]]-7-[[[(4-Ethyl-2,3-dioxo-1-piperazinyl)carbonyl]amino](4-hydroxy phenyl) acetyl]amino]-3-[[[(1-methyl-1H-tetrazol-5-yl)thio]methyl]-8-oxo-5-thia-1-azabicyclo[4.2.0]oct-2-ene-2-carboxylic acid. CEFO (Figure 1) is official drug in Indian Pharmacopoeia British Pharmacopoeia.[4-5] Tazobactam (TAZO) is a compound that inhibits the action of bacterial β -lactamase. TAZO is semi-synthetic parenteral penicillin with a wide range of antibacterial action. [6-7] Tazobactam (TAZO) chemically known as (2S,3S,5R)-3-Methyl-7-oxo-3-(1H-1,2,3-triazol-1-ylmethyl)-4-thia-1 azabicyclo[3.2.0]heptane-2-carboxylic acid 4,4-dioxide given in (Figure 2) TAZO is not official drug in any Pharmacopoeia. The combination of CEFO and TAZO is more powerful for the treatment of direct to serious contaminations than single medication treatment alone. CEFO and TAZO combination are utilized for the treatment of urinary tract infections and skin diseases. A literature survey uncovered that a liquid chromatography method has been reported for determination of CEFO in formulation.[8] CEFO in combination with other drugs also have been analyzed by various liquid chromatography methods.[9-11] TAZO was also successfully estimated by HPLC, HPTLC.[12-13] Present work includes the advancement of a basic RP-HPLC strategy for simultaneous estimation of CEFO and TAZO in bulk as well as in pharmaceutical formulation.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of Cefoperazone **Figure 2: Chemical structure of Tazobactam.**

High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)

HPLC uses a liquid mobile phase to isolate the segments of a mixture. These components (or analytes) are first disintegrated in a dissolvable, and afterward compelled to course through a chromatographic column under a high pressure. In the column, the mixture is settled into its parts. Subsequently, HPLC gets a high level of adaptability which is not found in other chromatographic frameworks and it can without much of a stretch separate a wide assortment of chemical mixtures. [14-15]

Method Development

Before beginning the method development, different physiochemical properties like pKa value, log P, solvency and absorption maximum of the drug must be known, for it establishes a framework for HPLC method development. Log P and solubility plays an important role for selection of mobile phase and sample solvent while pKa value is crucial as it helps determine the pH of the buffer and pH related changes in retention occur at pH values within ± 2 of pKa value.[16]

Limits of Degradation

The subject of how much debasement is adequate has been the point of numerous discourses among pharmaceutical researchers. Degradation of medication substances in the vicinity of 5% and 20% has been acknowledged as reasonable for validation of chromatographic assays. Some pharmaceutical researchers think 10% degradation is optimal for use in analytical validation for pharmaceuticals for which adequate stability limits of 90% of mark assert is normal. Others recommended that drug substance with a blend of known degradation products can be utilized to challenge the techniques utilized for monitoring stability of drug product. No such breaking points for physiochemical changes, loss of activity or degradation during shelf life have been built up for singular sorts or groups of biological products. Therefore it is not essential that forced degradation would effect in a degradation product. The method can be concluded if no degradation is observed after drug material or drug product remained exposed to stress conditions than those conditions cited in an accelerated stability protocol. [17]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The reference standard of CEFO and TAZO were gotten from Molecule Laboratory Pvt. Ltd, Ahmedabad, India. The fixed dose combination of CEFO and TAZO (Lupitam) was bought from the local pharmacy. Each unit of Lupitam contains 1000 mg of Cefoperazone and 125 mg of Tazobactam. The Acetonitrile (HPLC grade) and potassium dihydrogen phosphate (AR grade) were obtained from Chemox Enterprises, Company: Hexon Laboratories India.

Forced Degradation Studies. [18]

The goal of this Forced Degradation study is to show that the method developed is appropriate for estimating the assay of Cefoperazone and Tazobactam in presence of impurities and degradation products.

Preparation of solutions for forced degradation studies.

A) 0.1M Hydrochloric acid: 0.85 ml of HCL was diluted in 100ml of HPLC grade water to obtain 0.1 M HCL.

B) 0.1M Sodium hydroxide: 0.4 gm of NaOH was dissolved in 100 ml of HPLC grade water to obtain 0.1M NaOH.

C) 3% Hydrogen peroxide solution: 3% H₂O₂ was diluted to 10 ml using HPLC grade water to obtain 3% H₂O₂ solution.

Acid Degradation.

10 mg of pure drug was transferred to round bottom flask. To this, 10 ml of 0.1M HCL was added and this reaction mixture kept aside for 12 hrs. At room temperature, from that 0.12 ml solution is diluted to 10 ml with diluents to obtain concentration of 120 µg/ml. This solution was mixed well and was filtered through 0.45µm filter (Nylon filter) and injected onto column under optimized RP-HPLC conditions.

Alkali Degradation.

10 mg of pure drug was transferred to round bottom flask. To this, 10 ml of 0.1M NAOH was added and this reaction mixture kept aside for 12hrs. At 37°C, from that 0.12 ml solution is diluted to 10 ml with diluents to obtain concentration of 120µg/ml. This solution was mixed well and was filtered through 0.45µm filter (Nylon filter) and injected onto column under optimized RP-HPLC conditions.

Hydrogen Peroxide Degradation.

10 mg of pure drug was transferred to round bottom flask. To this 10 ml of 3% H₂O₂ was added and this reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for about 15 minutes. Further 0.12 ml of the above solution was diluted to 10ml with diluent to obtain concentration of 120 µg/ml. Mixed well and filter through 0.45µm filter and injected onto column under optimized RP-HPLC conditions.

Photolytic degradation.

The Cefoperazone and Tazobactam powder and solutions of both were prepared and exposed to light to determine the irradiation of light on the stability of solution and powder form of drugs. Approximately 100mg of drug powder and 1mg/ml solution were spread on a glass dish in a layer that was less than 2mm thickness and were placed in a light cabinet and exposed to UV light for 12hrs. Samples are removed after 12hrs and diluents to get a concentration of 200µg/ml solution and then injected.

Thermal degradation.

Sample powder equivalent to 100 mg of Cefoperazone and 12.5mg of Tazobactam was taken and kept in a controlled temperature oven at 80°C for 12hrs. After 12hrs the powder was diluted with diluents to get a concentration of 200 µg/ml solution.

Instrumentation and Chromatographic Conditions.

Chromatographic separation was performed using chromatography (Model no.: HPLC 3000 Series Company: Analytical Technologies Ltd.) system equipped with the Detector: UV-3000-M detector. HPLC Workstation software was employed for data collecting and processing Chromatographic separation was performed on BDS Hypersil Grace C18 (4.6ID x 250mm, Particle size: 5 micron). A binary mobile phase consisting 10 M potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer, pH 2.8 and acetonitrile (80:20 v/v) was delivered through a column at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. The phosphate buffer, pH 2.8 and acetonitrile was filtered separately through a 0.45 µm membrane filter paper. The mobile phase was degassed before use. HPLC analysis was performed at ambient temperature with detection at 254 nm. The injection volume was 20 µL.

Preparation of standard stock solution.**Standard stock solution of CEFO (400µg/mL):**

An accurately weighed quantity of powder equivalent to 40.0 mg of CEFO was transferred to 100 mL volumetric flask. The drug was dissolved and diluted up to the mark with acetonitrile

Standard stock solution of TAZO (50µg/mL):

An accurately weighed quantity of powder equivalent to 5.0 mg of TAZO was transferred to 100 mL volumetric flask. The drug was dissolved and diluted up to the mark with acetonitrile.

Assay of marketed formulation. [19]

10 vial units (Lupitam) were separately weighed and average weight was recorded. Dry powder from all vials was combined together to make a pooled sample. A quantity of vial powder (≅ 40.0 mg of CEFO and 5.0 mg of TAZO) was weighed and transferred into 100 mL of volumetric flask. The mixture was dissolved in acetonitrile, sonicated for 10 min and diluted to the up to mark with acetonitrile to obtain a concentration of 400 µg/mL of CEFO and 50 µg/mL of TAZO. The solution was filtered using Whatmann filter paper No. 41. This solution was further diluted with mobile phase to obtain final concentration of CEFO (40 µg/ml) and TAZO (5µg/ml). The final sample solution was filtered (Whatmann filter paper No. 41) and injected. Run time of analysis was kept 15 min and detection is carried out at 254 nm. All the determinations were carried out in triplicate.

METHOD VALIDATION. [20-21]

Validation of an analytical procedure is used to confirm that the analytical procedure employed for a specific test is suitable for its intended use. The developed chromatographic method was validated for accuracy, precision, linearity and range, system suitability, and robustness, as per ICH guidelines

System suitability test.

The system suitability test was performed making five injections of a standard solution and evaluating several chromatographic parameters such as resolution, area % reproducibility, and number of theoretical plates and tailing factor, presented in Table 1.

Analysis of marketed formulation.

Results of assay were in good agreement with the label claim. The drug content in the unit was found to be 98.94±1.00 % and 99.69±0.963% for Cefoperazone and Tazobactam, respectively, are shown in Table 2.

Linearity and range.

Working solutions were injected under the operating chromatographic conditions and peak areas for each drug were calculated at 254 nm. The calibration curve was plotted between areas against corresponding concentrations of each drug. Linear regression data for calibration curves were shown in Table 3. The range of solution has been decided according to correlation coefficient of regression equation.

Accuracy (% recovery).

Accuracy of the method was calculated by recovery studies at three levels by standard addition method. Percent recovery of CEFO and TAZO was determined at three different level 80%, 100% and 120% of the target concentration in triplicate, the results obtained were compared with expected results and statistically validated, are shown in Table 4.

Precision.

Inter-day and Intraday precision were performed in following concentration range 40µg/ml 120µg/ml and 200 µg/ml of CEFO and 5, 15, 25µg/ml of TAZO, respectively. At different time intervals in the same day and at the same time on different days. The variation in the results was analyzed and statistically validated. The % relative standard deviation (%RSD) values for inter-day and intra-day precision for CEFO and TAZO are shown in Table 5.

Robustness.

Influence of small changes in chromatographic conditions such as change in flow rate, that is, ±0.2 mL/min., change in pH (±0.2) and change in mobile phase (±2%v/v) was studied to determine the robustness of the method. Sample solution of 100% concentration is prepared and injected in triplicate for every condition and % Assay was calculated for each condition are shown in Table 6.

LOD and LOQ

The standard deviation of the Y-intercept and average slope of the calibration curve was used to calculate LOD and LOQ using following formulae.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \text{SD/S and LOQ} = 10 \times \text{SD/S}$$

LOD - Limit of detection,

LOQ – Limit of quantitation

Where, S is average value of slopes of calibration plots and SD is calculated using values of y intercepts of regression equations are shown in (Table 7).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first unique convenient stages were endeavored in attempt to show signs of improvement partition and good determination amongst CEFO and TAZO combined dosage form. The potassium dihydrogen phosphate (10 M KH₂PO₄) Buffer: Acetonitrile (80:20) at pH 2.8) mobile phase was appropriate for permitting decent separation of both compounds by using Grace C18 (4.6ID x 250mm, Particle estimate: 5 micron) at 40±5°C at 1mL/min. flow rate. As the CEFO and TAZO demonstrates remarkable absorbance at wavelength 254 nm, therefore it was employed as detection wavelength for simultaneous estimation of CEFO and TAZO marketed formulation. These optimized conditions had acceptable system suitability parameters indicate good resolution for both the peaks (Table 1). The Percent recovery examine of CEFO and TAZO in sterile dried powder sample were 98.94% and 99.69%, separately (Table 2). The estimation of % Relative Standard Deviation (%RSD) was 0.1053 and 0.1415 for CEFO and TAZO, respectively, indicates reproducibility of the method. The Number of hypothetical plates for CEFO and TAZO were 10774 and 19308, respectively, that are in acceptance limit. Tailing Factor for CEFO and TAZO were 1.22 and 1.00, respectively, not more than 2 and these qualities were satisfactory and in this manner the improved conditions were utilized for facilitate examination. The Retention time for CEFO and TAZO were 3.647 and 4.671 min., respectively (Figure 3,4).

The estimations of correlation coefficient for CEFO and TAZO (Table 3) demonstrated the good relationship between peak area and concentration. In this manner, the technique created was linear in concentration range of 40-200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for CEFO and 5-40 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for TAZO. Percent assay was $99.34 \pm 0.70\%$ for CEFO and $100.25 \pm 0.51\%$ for TAZO showed accuracy. The high recovery obtained indicates that the proposed method is highly accurate. The low estimation of % RSD in intra-day and between day accuracy showed reproducibility of this technique (Table 5). At extensive think variations were made to check the noteworthy variations in test conditions proposed robustness of developed method (Table 6). LOD and LOQ for CEFO was 3.77, 11.43 that for TAZO was 0.1146 & 0.3470, individually (Table 7). The detail Summary of Forced degradation data for Cefoperazone and Tazobactam is given (Table 8). Several trials has made until getting good peak resolution, acceptable plate count and tailing factor.

Figure 3: Standard Solution of CEFO and TAZO.

Figure 4: Sample solution of CEFO and TAZO.

Figure 5: Calibration curve of Cefoperazone.

Figure 6: Calibration curve of Tazobactam.

Chromatograms of Forced degradation studies.
Acid Degradation

Figure 7. Chromatogram of acid degradation (0.1M HCl, 12hrs at 80°C).

Base induced degradation:

Figure 8. Chromatogram of base degradation (0.1M NaOH, 12hrs at 80°C).

Hydrogen Peroxide Degradation:**Figure 11. Chromatogram of photolytic degradation (HPLC grade water, 12hrs at 80°C).**

Table 1: Results of system suitability test.

Parameter	Cefoperazone	Tazobactam
SD*	41779	576
%RSD*	0.1053	0.1415
RT(min)	3.647	4.671
Theoretical Plate	3690	12185
Tailing Factor	1.22	1.00

*n=5.

Table 2: Results of Assay of Marketed formulation.

Parameters	Cefoperazone	Tazobactam
Label Claim (mg)	1000	125
Actual content found (mg)	989.4	124.62
% Avg. Assay(n=3)	98.94	99.69

Table 3: Linear regression data for calibration curves of Cefoperazone and Tazobactam.

Parameters	Cefoperazone	Tazobactam
Linearity range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	40-200	5-40
Coefficient of correlation	0.9997	0.9996
Slope	36538	16596
Intercept	41940	90880

Table 4: Accuracy data of CEFO and TAZO.

Drug	Amount Added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount recovered ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Mean % Recovery $\pm$ SD*	% RSD*
CEFO	80% (32 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)	32.04	100.12% $\pm$ 0.3452	0.3447
	100% (40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)	39.55	98.89% $\pm$ 0.1567	0.1584
	120% (48 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)	47.53	99.03% $\pm$ 0.0412	0.0420
TAZO	80% (4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)	4.01	100.32% $\pm$ 0.042	0.0421
	100% (5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)	5.00	100.20% $\pm$ 0.171	0.1787
	120% (6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)	6.01	100.25% $\pm$ 0.025	0.0259

*n=3.

Table 5: Precision data of Cefoperazone and Tazobactam.

Parameter	Cefoperazone	Tazobactam
Inter-day(%RSD)*	0.4606	0.6179
Intra-day(%RSD)*	0.7839	0.4352

*n=6).

Table 6: Robustness studies of CEFO and TAZO.

Change in flow rate(1ml/min)	Flow rate(ml/min)	Average*	Std. Dev	%RSD
Cefoperazone	1.2ml/min	1124172	11145.492	0.99144
	0.8ml/min	1136675	187.960	0.01653
Tazobactam	1.2ml/min	80182	152.79	0.19056
	0.8ml/min	80751	262.67	0.32528
Change in mobile phase composition Buffer: Acetonitrile(80:20)v/v	Mobile phase(80:20)v/v	Average*	Std. Dev	%RSD
Cefoperazone	(78:22)v/v	1257875	6560.765	0.521575
	(82:18)v/v	1099395	2082.794	0.189448
Tazobactam	(78:22)v/v	81932.67	109.294	0.133396
	(82:18)v/v	81188.66	143.196	0.176375
Change in pH(2.8) ±0.2	Change in pH	Average*	Std. Dev	%RSD
Cefoperazone	3	1025331	1721.78	0.167925
	2.6	1235159	2790.93	0.225957
Tazobactam	3	80818.6	123.293	0.152556
	2.6	80216.6	123.066	0.153417

*n=3.

Table 7: LOD and LOQ.

Parameter	Cefoperazone	Tazobactam
LOD	3.77	0.1146
LOQ	11.43	0.3470

Table No: 8 Summary of Forced degradation data for Cefoperazone and Tazobactam:

Stress Condition	Time (hrs.)	Retention Time	Time (hrs.)	Retention Time
As such	12hrs	3.647	12hrs	4.671
Acid Hydrolysis (0.1 N, at RT)	12hrs	3.773	12hrs	4.696
Base Hydrolysis (0.1N at RT)	12hrs	3.757	12hrs	4.674
Oxidation (5% H ₂ O ₂ at RT)	12hrs	3.675	12hrs	4.658
Photolysis(UV Light and sunlight)	12hrs	3.660	12hrs	4.683
Thermal (at 80 ⁰ c)	12hrs	3.667	12hrs	4.707

CONCLUSION

The present work speaks to the report that arrangements with simultaneous analysis of Cefoperazone and Tazobactam in bulk and sterile dried injection dosage forms using RP-HPLC. It can be concluded from the results that the proposed method is simple, accurate, robust and precise. This method was validated as per ICH guidelines. Thus, it can be used for normal analysis of Cefoperazone and Tazobactam.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors have declared that no conflict of interests exists.

REFERENCES

1. Fauci AS, Touchette NA, Folkers GK. Emerging Infectious Diseases: a 10-Year Perspective. National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases. *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 2005;11(4):2-13.
2. Kumar SA, Shetty YR, Ahmed M, Sridhar BK, Kumar VML. Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for quantitative estimation of cefoperazone in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms. *Int. J. Chem Tech Res* 2011;3:1075-79
3. Dhandapani B, Thirumoorthy N, Shaik HR, Rama KM. RP-HPLC method development and validation for the simultaneous estimation of cefoperazone and salbactam in parenteral preparation. *Int. J. Chem Tech Res* 2010;2:752
4. *Indian Pharmacopoeia*, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India 2010; 1-2:p.1014.
5. *British Pharmacopoeia*, British Pharmacopoeia Commission, London 2009;2:p.1144.
6. Bhavana M, Reddy RT, Sandhya M, Umea V, Rao M. RP-HPLC method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of cefepime and tazobactam in marketed formulation. *Int. J. Pharm* 2013;3:837-42.

7. Tamboli SR, Patil DD. RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of cefepime hydrochloride and tazobactam sodium in bulk and pharmaceuticals. *Journal of Chemistry* 2013;1-6.
8. Lalitha N, Pawar V, Puranik S.B, Pai P.N and Rao G. K: Estimation of cefoperazone in marketed formulation by RP-HPLC. *Orient J Chem* 2008;24:737-40.
9. Lalitha N, Puranik SB, Pai PN. A Stability-Indicating HPLC Method for Cefoperazone. *Eurasian J Anal Chem* 2009;4:110-18.
10. Kumar VK, Dharuman J, Karuna A. RP-HPLC method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of sulbactam and cefoperazone in dosage form and in plasma. *Int J Pharm. Bio. Sci* 2010;4:87-92
11. Abdullah N.A, Ayad M.F and El-Kosasy A.M: HPLC and Densitometric TLC methods for simultaneous determination of pazufloxacin with some co-administered drugs in human plasma. *Chromatography Separation Techniques* 2012;3:1-8.
12. Rao LA, Sai KK, Kiran Kumar CH, Raja T. Simultaneous determination of Piperacillin and Tazobactam in bulk and Pharmaceutical dosage forms by RPHPLC. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci* 2011;3:134-6.
13. Malgundkar SS, Mulla S. Validated HPTLC method for simultaneous determination of ceftriaxone sodium and tazobactam sodium in combined dosage. *Form. J Pharm Biol Sci* 2014;9:60-5.
14. Connors K.A. *A Textbook of Pharmaceutical Analysis*. New York: Wiley- Interscience; 8th ed. 1999:p.408-21.
15. Sethi P.D. *High Performance Liquid Chromatography, Quantitative Analysis of Pharmaceutical Formulations*. 1st ed.; New Delhi: CBS Publishers and Distributor 2001: p.3-11,116-120,60-65.
16. Rao VB, Naga SG, Ajitha A, Maheshwara U, Rao V. A Review on stability indicating HPLC method development. *World J Pharm Pharm Sci* 2015;8:405-423.
17. Blessy M, Ruchi D. Patel, Prajesh N. Prajapati and Y.K. Agrawal: Development of forced degradation and stability indicating studies of drugs: A review. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Analysis* 2014;4(3):159-165.
18. Bakshi M, Singh S. Development of validated stability-indicating assay methods—critical review. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis* 2002;28: 1011-40.
19. Ranjale AR, Jain HK. Development and method validation of RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of cefoperazone and tazobactam in marketed formulation *Int. J Pharm Pharm Sc.* 2014;6:462-65.
20. ICH Q2 (R1): *Validation of Analytical Procedures: Text and Methodology*, ICH Harmonized Tripartite Guideline, Geneva Switzerland, 2003.
21. Kim DW, Yousaf AM, Li DX, Kim JO, Yong CS, Cho KH, Choi H. Development of RP-HPLC method for simultaneous determination of docetaxel and curcumin in rat plasma: validation and stability. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 2017; 2:105-113.

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